

LAR@Home 2026 Team Description Paper

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Abstract. This paper describes the development and progress of the team LAR@Home from the University of Minho, Portugal, for the RoboCup@Home competition that will take place in Incheon, South Korea, in 2026. After the robot's participation in the 2023 and 2024 editions of RoboCup, the team focused on improving and adding novel different technologies to enhance the overall set of CHARMIE's capabilities. These improvements encompass new navigation skills, with special focus on Reinforcement Learning for unmapped environments. The creation of a virtual radar using different sensors to improve obstacle awareness and detection. Improved localisation with the addition of new sensors and filtering. Improved manipulation for picking and placing a wide range of differently shaped objects. A new face for a more natural Human-Robot Interaction. A dual LLM system for general purpose command understanding. Among other new skills further described in this document.

1 Introduction

The Laboratory of Automation and Robotics (LAR) is a RoboCup team affiliated with the University of Minho, Portugal, competing in both the Football Middle Size League (LAR@MSL), the @Home League (LAR@Home) and now taking the first steps in the Humanoid League (LAR@Humanoids). In 2020, the team started the development of CHARMIE, a robot whose name stands for Collaborative Home/Healthcare Assistant Robot by Minho Industrial Electronics. In 2023, CHARMIE made its debut at RoboCup in Bordeaux, France, achieving 7th place. In 2024, the team participated again, this time earning 5th place and tripling its score compared to the previous year, highlighting significant advancements in the robot's capabilities. This team description paper is part of the qualification package for RoboCup 2026, which will take place in Incheon, South Korea, in the RoboCup@Home League, and outlines the progress of the LAR@Home project. The focus for the 2026 competition lies in incorporating new technologies, refining existing functionalities, and improving the overall performance of the robot.

Historically, LAR has been an active contributor to RoboCup since 1999 in the MSL League and has participated for the first time in the @Home League in 2010. The team was the first to introduce a three-wheeled omnidirectional platform in the @Home League, showcasing its innovative approach to robotics. In addition to competing, LAR has been dedicated to promoting the @Home League and fostering its growth. In 2022, the team organised the @Home Educational event in Guimarães, Portugal, alongside

the European RoboCup Junior competition. To address the lack of a European RoboCup@Home preparation events since the last German Open in 2019, LAR hosted the Portugal Open in Tomar, Portugal, in April 2023 where the LAR@Home team finished in 3rd place. Recognising the importance of such events, the team also organised the Portugal Open 2024 in Paredes de Coura, finishing in 1st place. The team is currently planning and organising the Portugal Open 2026. In January 2025, LAR@Home participated in the first European @Home workshop in Eindhoven, Netherlands. In addition, the team has actively contributed to the Technical Committee for RoboCup@Home 2025 and 2026.

This document is structured as follows: Section 2 details the mechanical design of the robot, Section 3 presents the work conducted on software development, and Section 4 concludes with a summary of the progress achieved.

2 Mechanical Description

The CHARMIE (see annex 5.1) mobile manipulator follows a design inspired by humans to enhance human-robot interaction. Wheeled locomotion was chosen for its efficiency in flat interiors. The base incorporates four omni wheels set at 90° to enhance manoeuvrability, each with an independent suspension system to maintain continuous contact of all wheels with the ground and improve the robot's stability. Some enhancements were applied to the suspension system to increase durability and quality. Additionally, the position of the robot's microphone and speakers was adjusted to emulate human anatomy, placing them in proximity to the robot's face. To expand the robot's operational workspace, an articulated trunk with two degrees of freedom was developed. This trunk allows the robot to perform linear crouching movements and flex its trunk forward. Static balancing and the use of self-locking linear actuators were implemented in both movements to reduce energy consumption [1]. A bearing system has also been incorporated to minimise oscillations in the torso. CHARMIE is equipped with UFactory's xArm 6 robotic arm, with 6 degrees of freedom, a reach of 70 cm and a weight of 12.2 kg. The arm includes a gripper capable of handling objects with an opening range of 85 cm, resulting in an arm payload of 3 kg. In addition, an Intel RealSense D405 depth camera has been placed at the top of the gripper's base to help improve the spatial awareness in relation to the objects position. To create a more friendly and relatable interaction, the robot presents a portable monitor with touchscreen display as the new face. This face enables the expression of emotions and provides a visual interface for communicating detected objects or people to the human user. Additionally, the robot's face changes to reflect different states, such as listening attentively when awaiting input from a user. The robot is enhanced with two Hokuyo URG-04LX-UG01 LiDARs, a Livox MID 360 LiDAR and a Orbbec Astra Pro Plus camera, all mounted on the base platform optimising navigation for improved obstacle avoidance, particularly with small objects. It also incorporates an Intel RealSense D455 RGBD camera, coupled with Shure V5 microphone and speakers, ensuring advanced visual and audio sensing capabilities for a versatile robotic system. The robot's neck has two degrees of freedom in series, controlled by rotary motors (Dynamixel MX-64),

enabling it to bend and rotate. The resulting weight of the robot is 80 kg, and its height ranges between 128 cm and 142 cm. In addition to the up/down movement, the robot flexes its torso forward, reaching a minimum height of 92 cm. The torso and arm can pass under structures, such as tables, up to 80 cm, allowing the robot to reach objects on the floor that are 60 cm away from the robot platform.

3 CHARMIE Functionalities

This section details the software developments for the robot CHARMIE, highlighting enhancements and new functionalities introduced. The primary focus over the last year has been an update to navigation, localisation, obstacle awareness and avoidance, the creation of an open-source virtual radar system with easy integration of any obstacle detection sensor, object manipulation, furniture interaction, a new face system for improved natural human-robot interaction and a dual LLM system for understanding general purpose commands. All the software developed for the robot is built for ROS2. The code is designed in a modular manner, enabling functionalities to be used as needed. The ROS2 architecture has been optimised to enhance communication between all the robot's components, fully leveraging its real-time capabilities.

3.1 Localisation

The localisation system combines data from various sensors and middleware to accurately determine the robot's position within a mapped environment. For odometry, an Extended Kalman Filter is used to fuse: motor encoders from wheel movement, IMU data, and an estimation of 2D odometry based on planar laser scans. The localisation top layer uses Adaptive Monte Carlo Localisation (AMCL). While odometry provides an estimate of the robot's position based on wheel movements, IMU data and planar laser scans, AMCL enhances this estimate by using a pre-defined map, ensuring precise localisation within the environment.

3.2 Low Level

The low-level control system manages communication with all the robot's hardware components. This includes controlling the torso positions, handling limit switches, interacting with the RGB LEDs (used as a primary debugging tool), operating the emergency buzzer, reading the start button and mode setting buttons located inside the robot. This control system is also responsible for all communications with the motor boards. Managing setting speeds, reading encoders, safety watchdog timers, safety currents and voltages, closed-loop control that guarantees the robot moves at the correct speed independently of external factors such as slopes or small protuberances.

3.3 Virtual Radar

The virtual radar system is implemented as a modular ROS2 node that fuses heterogeneous range sensors into a unified, low-dimensional representation tailored for both classical navigation and reinforcement learning. It is fully configured through a YAML file, where the user specifies the robot base frame, robot radius, update frequency, angular coverage and number of sectors, as well as an arbitrary list of observation sources. Each sensor—whether LaserScan or PointCloud2—is processed according to its individual geometric and operational constraints, filtered, and transformed into the robot base frame. The system then merges all valid points and discretises the surrounding space into angular sectors, computing for each the minimum distance to nearby obstacles. These distances, both raw and normalised, are published alongside a compact sector-based representation that abstracts the complexity of full point clouds into a lightweight, radar-like format. A dedicated service allows querying obstacle proximity in any direction, enabling efficient integration with high-level decision-making and reinforcement learning policies. This architecture provides a flexible and extensible sensing layer where new sensors can be added seamlessly, ensuring consistent and robust environmental perception across diverse setups.

3.4 Navigation

CHARMIE currently integrates three complementary navigation systems, each optimised for different operational scenarios: Non-Linear Dynamic Systems for Navigation (custom-developed by the team), the ROS 2 Navigation Stack (Nav2), and a Reinforcement Learning based navigation framework for unmapped environments using a custom virtual radar sensor. The selection of the navigation module is performed based on map availability, the level of environmental dynamicity, the suitability of omnidirectional motion, safety, and overall efficiency.

In the custom Non-Linear Dynamic Systems Navigation framework, the robot identifies static and dynamic obstacles within a predefined radius and defines a target pose using either rotation or translation commands. Navigation toward this target is achieved through a distributed control architecture built upon non-linear dynamical systems. The navigation vector field integrates task constraints by combining attractive forces that guide CHARMIE toward the goal with repulsive forces that modulate trajectories to avoid collisions. As the relative configuration of obstacles and target evolves, these forces adapt continuously, ensuring both safety and convergence to the goal. A key characteristic of this method is its emphasis on maintaining the robot's front orientated towards the direction of motion, improving human interpretability of the robot's movement and provide optimal use of the robot's forward-facing sensing suite.

The ROS 2 Navigation Stack (Nav2) is a modular, behaviour-tree-driven framework for autonomous navigation in known environments. It integrates global and local planning, behaviour trees for task sequencing, map-based localisation, obstacle avoidance, and recovery behaviours. Nav2 allows robots to compute safe trajectories to

a target pose while continuously reacting to dynamic obstacles through real-time local planning. For CHARMIE, several improvements to the standard Nav2 pipeline were implemented: Secondary map server for manual obstacle layers, enabling the addition of map-based obstacles used exclusively for avoidance but not for localisation. Enhanced recovery behaviours. Integration of the Rotation Shim Controller, which improves behaviour in narrow spaces and reduces unwanted recovery activations. Configurable locomotion mode, allowing the robot to dynamically switch between omnidirectional and differential-like movement patterns.

Beyond classical and map-based navigation, the team is developing a Reinforcement Learning (RL) navigation framework [2] designed specifically for unmapped or highly dynamic environments, such as restaurants, or semi-structured public spaces. To support this effort, CHARMIE has been fully integrated into NVIDIA Isaac Lab, enabling high-fidelity simulation with accurate physics, sensor modelling, and domain randomisation. Within this simulated environment, the robot is trained to navigate using a custom virtual radar, a lightweight, computationally efficient sensor that aggregates environmental geometry into angular sectors. This radar abstraction simplifies perception and makes policy learning more sample-efficient than full point cloud or image-based observation. The objective of this RL module is to learn end-to-end policies capable of avoiding dynamic obstacles, reaching targets without prior maps, and generalising new indoor layouts. By combining domain randomisation, curriculum learning, and physics-based simulation, the learnt policies are expected to provide CHARMIE with a robust fallback navigation technique suitable for map-free deployment in real-world environments where traditional SLAM-based methods are unreliable or unavailable.

3.5 Face

The current version of CHARMIE's face introduces a new touchscreen display. The software developed aims to create an HMI module that is universally suitable for any interaction necessary. It allows the robot to change facial expressions (being able to display happiness or sleepiness if in idle mode). It can also transform the screen into a keyboard or touch-button menu to provide an alternative input method to the audio system. Visually indicate when the robot is communicating (such as indicating when it is listening or calibrating audio levels) to make said communication more natural. Additionally, the face can display images and display text, which can be used as a visual aid to the robot's verbal communication.

3.6 Audio

For audio recognition, CHARMIE currently uses Whisper, an automatic speech recognition model. With Whisper's capabilities, CHARMIE can recognize and understand speech in a variety of languages, accents, and acoustic environments. To enhance its performance, the team has developed custom features, including a dynamic ambient noise calibration tool and a speech detection system that identifies the start and end of speech. This improves natural communication by ensuring accurate recognition

at the conclusion of spoken commands, as well as increasing time efficiency. Additionally, a "continuous mode" has been implemented, where the robot remains idle or performs tasks until a specific word or command is detected. A training mode has also been created for custom words, such as diminutives or words with added prefixes and suffixes, that are not included in the standard dictionary. Furthermore, the team has integrated MediaPipe audio classification to recognize sounds like clapping, whistles, and knocking. Importantly, the entire audio pipeline, along with all its features, operates entirely offline.

3.7 People Detection

For people detection, CHARMIE uses YOLO Pose, a pose estimation model based on YOLO (You Only Look Once). This model identifies keypoints in a human figure in an image, providing confidence scores for each point. This enables the robot to detect people and determine their position in space. Additionally, custom adaptations have been developed to enhance the detection of individuals with their arms raised, a gesture commonly used in various contexts. This allows the robot to not only identify all individuals present but also determine which person it should interact with.

3.8 Object Manipulation

For CHARMIE's pick-and-place manipulation of a wide variety of household objects in an autonomous way, two different methodologies were adopted: Standard Manipulation Routine and MoveIt!.

Standard Manipulation Routine starts by locating the intended object, using YOLO and a filtering algorithm, ensuring the correct target is located. The robot determines the best grasping mode based on the object's height, shape and accessibility. The arm moves into a pre-grasp calculated configuration. The camera located at the gripper's base provides close-range depth information to refine the gripper's alignment. The robot applies small linear corrections based on feedback to ensure the end-effector can grasp the object. The gripper closes with an internal check that confirms whether the object was successfully grasped. If not, the robot follows a controlled help-request protocol. Once the object is secured, CHARMIE retracts the arm into the default position or prepares for placement or handover.

MoveIt! can be used by CHARMIE as an alternative to generate safe, collision-free trajectories during manipulation tasks. MoveIt! receives the robot's kinematic model, the current joint states, the target pose of the end-effector, computed from the detected object's position, and a representation of the surrounding environment. Using this information, the framework plans feasible trajectories that avoid obstacles and respect joint limits, guiding the arm smoothly from its current state to the desired grasping pose. This provides a robust, motion-planning-centric alternative to the robot's custom manipulation routines.

3.9 GUI

A graphical user interface was developed to improve monitoring of CHARMIE and for showcase demonstrations. It includes a debug system that displays all active ROS2 nodes and flags any issues, tools for activating the visual detection systems (people, objects, and furniture), and live views from all onboard cameras with their detection outputs, with the option to switch between feeds. The GUI also features a localisation tool that visualises all detected data on the map.

3.10 LLM

To improve CHARMIE's capabilities in human-robot interaction, the team is working on developing a natural instruction comprehension system based on two Large Language Models, using the OpenAI GPT-4o APIs. The first model, the normalisation module, filters and interprets the user's natural-language command. It extracts the essential information, resolves ambiguities, and adapts the instruction to the robot's internal knowledge base and operational context. This ensures that all commands are mapped into CHARMIE's known vocabulary and actionable domains, producing a clean, standardised instruction for execution. The second model, the sequencing module, transforms the normalised command into a structured sequence of low-level robot actions. It decomposes broad and high-level intents into specific, executable skills and uses function calling to trigger predefined robot functions directly, ensuring a reliable execution plan. Figure Fig. 1 illustrates this system workflow with an example.

Fig. 1. LLM example interaction

Once this functionality is validated, the team will focus on running the LLMs locally and fully offline, aligning with one of CHARMIE's core development goals: maintaining autonomy without depending on external connectivity.

In parallel, the team is studying the integration of a Vision-Language Model (VLM) to reduce the need for manually curated object datasets. With this model, CHARMIE will be able to identify objects and scene elements on the fly, eliminating the requirement for continuous dataset training and image cataloguing.

4 Conclusions and Future Work

This article presents CHARMIE's current architecture and continuous improvements made by the team ever since the team's participation in the RoboCup@Home 2024 competition. The most significant updates regard manipulation speed and accuracy, assisted by a 2D object orientation algorithm. Advancements to the safety, speed and reliability of the robot's navigation through Nav2 and RL. Addition of functionalities to the face module. A further expansion of the robot's spatial awareness due to an increased amount of sensory data from the resulting fusion of new and existing sensors.

Currently the team is actively working on implementing a new dual LLM system to expand CHARMIE's ability to understand and interact with users, enabling the robot to complete new kinds of natural language processing tasks. The team is currently exploring the advantages of implementing a second arm, which would expand the robot's manipulation workspace, increase the speed at which the robot completes tasks, allow it to handle two objects at a time, and provide new functional grasping strategies. Such as being able to hold an object with one arm and using the other arm to, for example, open the lid of said object. Additional minor improvements the team is also currently working on include replacing the current heavier batteries with smaller and lighter batteries to make transportation overseas easier. Further stabilisation of the torso with an additional support, and a redesign of CHARMIE's head shape to make it more aesthetically appealing to a general audience.

More details about the robot's hardware and software can be found in the extended 2021 article [3]. For those interested, our public repository for the CHARMIE project is available at: https://github.com/SparkRibeiro21/charmie_ws

References

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5 Annex

5.1 Hardware Description

- Base: Omnidirectional wheeled drive*
- Dimensions (mm): (w)560 (d)560 (h)1430-1570
- Weight: 80 kg
- Arm: UFACTORY xArm 6 DoF Robotic Arm
- PC: Lenovo LEGION 5
- GPU: NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3070
- Battery: Green Cell E-bike Battery 36V 20Ah
- RGB strip: 96 addressable LEDs*
- Tray: 3D Printed Tray with add-ons*
- Mobile Base:
 - 2D LiDAR: Hokuyo URG-04LX-UG01
 - 3D LiDAR: Livox MID 360
 - Camera: Orbbec Astra Pro Plus
 - IMU: CMPS12
 - Motor Controller: 2xMD49
 - Motors: 4xZGX45RM
- Torso:
 - Movement: 2x Linear Actuators*
 - IMU: 2xCMPS12
- Head:
 - Camera: Intel Realsense D455
 - Neck: Dual Dynamixel MX-64*
 - Face: Touchscreen display
 - Microphone: Shure MV5
 - Speakers: Dual USB 3W (70dB)
- Gripper:
 - Camera: Intel Realsense D405

5.2 Software Description

- OS: Ubuntu 22.04 LTS
- Middleware: ROS2 Humble
- Localisation: AMCL + EKF for Odometry
- Navigation: Non-Linear Dynamic Systems* / NAV2 / RL for unmapped environments*
- Object Recognition: YOLOv11 + TensorRT
- People Recognition: YOLOv11 Pose TensorRT
- Speech Recognition: Whisper
- Audio Classification: MediaPipe
- Speech Generation: coqui.ai
- Arm Control: MoveIt2
- LLM: Chat GPT API

* custom made by LAR@Home

Fig. 2. Front and rear view of CHARMIE